

The initial box vectors, the number of water molecules, and ions, and the length of the simulations are given. The last column specifies the source of the initial configuration. Models 1-3 are the top scoring cofilin-decorated actin filaments constructed as described in Supplementary Methods. The HFD-capped systems, H1' and H2', were generated by docking HFD and the HFD-free system, B2', was generated by removing HFD starting from the indicated configurations.

Systems	No.	X / Å	Y / Å	Z / Å	N _{water}	N _{Na}	N _{Cl}	Time / μs	Initial Configuration
HFD-bound	H1	145	126	196	90000	279	206	2.42	model 1
	H2	146	126	196	90000	279	206	2.28	model 2
	H3	146	125	197	90000	279	206	1.12	model 3
	H1'	145	125	220	100000	306	233	1.97	B1 - t= 2.42 μs
	H2'	145	125	221	100000	306	233	2.32	B2 - t= 0.94 μs
HFD-free	B1	147	123	223	100000	306	233	2.03	model 1
	B2	146	123	223	100000	306	233	2.01	model 2
	B3	146	123	223	100000	306	233	1.61	model 3
	B2'	146	123	201	90000	279	206	2.11	H2 - t= 0.76 μs